

DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN MULTIAXIAL FATIGUE OF SHORT FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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SUMMARY

The fatigue behaviour of a short fibre reinforced PBT-PET is investigated. To reduce the amount of fatigue tests necessary for semi-empirical models, the damage mechanisms are studied. Therefore, we employ thermographical tracking, surface replica technique and fracture surface observations. A damage scenario of the composite is then proposed.

Keywords: fatigue mechanisms, short-glass-fibre reinforced thermoplastic, PBT

INTRODUCTION

One of the concerns in the design of automotive components is the reduction of weight to increase dynamic vehicle behaviour and to reduce CO₂ emissions. But also high production rates and low costs are wished. Short fibre reinforced thermoplastics can meet these specifications and furthermore they can be moulded into complex forms. However, the fatigue behaviour must be taken into account to design cyclic stressed parts. Hence, different authors worked on this topic in the last decades.

Mandell [1] worked on a broad range of different short fibre reinforced polymer systems. He highlights that the fatigue failure mechanisms depend largely on the composition of the studied material system. Lang [2] worked on the fatigue crack propagation of polyamide and polystyrene systems. He found a stable crack propagation surface to appear ductile for the nylon system and probably with craze formation for the polystyrene system. The unstable crack propagation surface was found to be brittle. Horst [3] studied the SN fatigue behaviour of a short fibre reinforced PA6. The fracture surfaces after fatigue cycling until rupture present a brittle and a ductile zone. The latter is then interpreted as a fatigue crack on the basis of fracture mechanics. Damage is initiated at the fibres ends in the form of voids which grow and lead to unbonding of the complete fibre end. These microcracks will coalesce into a macrocrack and lead to final rupture.

In the past, fatigue mechanisms studies were based on scanning electron microscope (SEM) observations of the failure surface [1-4]. But also other techniques were used: hysteresis/elasticity measurement [4,6], cross section observation [4], photoelasticity [5], acoustic emission [5-6], fibre length measuring before/after fatigue tests [4], surface roughness measurement [7].

The present study contributes to the understanding of the fatigue mechanisms of a short-fibre-reinforced PBT-PET. We use different techniques in order to address different issues of the fatigue damage process: elasticity/hysteresis measurement, SEM observation, replica technique, thermography. This work is a first step in the development of a multiaxial fatigue criterion based on micromechanics.

EXPERIMENTAL

The investigated material is a mixture of polybutylene terephthalate, polyethylene terephthalate and short glass fibres (PBT-PET GF30). The specimens were cut out of an end line gated injection moulded plate longitudinal to Mouldflow direction as shown in figure 1. Two different kinds of dogbone specimens were used. Specimen A presents a dog bone formed specimen with 30 x 30 x 3 mm stressed volume (design LBF) while the dimensions of specimen B are divided by a factor of five which facilitates to keep track of all the stressed volume (6 x 6 x 3 mm) by the replica technique. While all tests are carried out on specimen A, the replica test was the only to be carried out on specimen B.

Figure 1: (a.) Injected plate and specimen positions. (b.) Specimen dimensions.

The static and fatigue tests were carried out on an Instron 1251 servo-hydraulic test system. All fatigue tests were load controlled at a minimum/maximum load ratio of $R = 0.1$ with a sinusoidal wave form. Tests were conducted in an air conditioned laboratory environment and the test frequencies were chosen to result in a surface heating of the specimens inferior to 4°C . Based on preliminary tests we conclude that higher frequencies resulting in higher heating will reduce fatigue lifetimes while lower frequencies do not change fatigue lifetimes significantly.

For the stress/strain curves and for hysteresis loop measurements, we use an Instron extensometer with 27.5 mm gage length. The tensile modulus is calculated according to ISO 527. The cross head speed is 1 mm/min for the tensile tests at room temperature and 500 mm/min for the cryogenic tensile test. The dynamic modulus, the damping energy and the mean deformation is computed based on the formulae given by Altstädt [8].

For the replica technique, the specimens were first wet ground with silicon carbide paper up to 4000 mesh, then polished with a 3 and a 1 micron diamond paste consecutively. The replica itself was obtained by applying Coltène President light body, a silicone-based impression material.

The fracture surfaces and the replicas were sputter-coated with palladium. The fractographic images were then taken on a JEOL JSM 6400 scanning electron microscope with an accelerating voltage of 7 kV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Material characterisation

We investigate the microstructure in the centre of the injected plate i.e. in the centre of the longitudinal dogbone specimen. Often, the loaded section of specimens is observed by light microscopy. The interpretation of these polished cuts rests difficult without image analysis software because the probability to find fibres normal to the plane is quite higher than to find fibres which lie in the plane. Therefore, we observe in the plane cuts which were obtained by grounding off consecutively 50 microns of thickness of the material. As the fibre orientation can be expected mainly planar [3], this technique gives us an insight in the fibre orientation in different thicknesses of the specimen.

From 0 to 200 micron thickness we find fibres aligned randomly as shown in figure 2.a. From 200 to 1250 micron we find the fibres oriented in longitudinal direction, figure 2.b. From 1250 to 1400 micron the fibres are oriented randomly again. Finally in the centre of the specimen from 1400 to 1500 micron fibres are oriented transversally, figure 2.c. We present the fibre orientation of the upper half of the composite's section in figure 2.d. as the fibre orientation is symmetric to the centreline. These results can be explained by rheological considerations for this plate geometry and are in good correlation to other results [3].

Figure 2: (a.) Random alignment. (b.) Longitudinal alignment. (c.) Transversal alignment. (d.) Observed fibre orientations of the upper half of the specimen section.

The fibre length distribution has been derived following the technique of Fu [9] by fibre length measuring with light microscopy images and a Matlab routine. The resulting corrected mean fibre length is 227 micron (1006 fibres) and the mean fibre diameter is

10.4 ± 1.1 micron (130 fibres), figure 3 a. and figure 3.b. The fibre content was 0,175 ± 0,001 measured by pyrolysing the matrix material of three samples.

Figure 3: Distribution functions of (a.) fibre diameter. (b.) fibre length.

The results of the static tensile tests are shown in figure 3.a. For this kind of loading very little dispersion is observed. The material behaviour is fragile. The ultimate tensile strength is 122.7 ± 1.2 and the Young's modulus is 9899 ± 22MPa.

Figure 4: (a.) Stress/strain curves for tensile tests. (b.) S-N data.

SN data for this kind of material is best described by a Basquin type law where σ_a is the stress amplitude, σ_f is the stress amplitude extrapolated to one cycle and m is the slope of the curve, equation 1 [1]. The blue diamond symbols present the S-N curve for the described test conditions. We obtain a slope m of 18 and the value for σ_f is 58.9 MPa.

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_f \cdot N^{-1/m} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

The black square symbol is an interrupted SN test which will be compared to a continuous test at the same stress level. Last, the red circle symbol presents a test at the medium stress level for which the replica technique was applied. The longer lifetime is eventually due to the reduction of the highly stressed volume compared to the A-type specimen as the B-type specimen was used.

Hysteresis evolution

To find out more about the fatigue mechanisms we carry out hysteresis loop measurements. The dynamic modulus, the damping energy and the mean strain are reported to reflect the fatigue damage [8].

To decouple dynamic modulus and hysteresis curve evolution from temperature, we carry out an interrupted fatigue test and compare it to a continuous test at the same stress level of $\sigma_a = 36$ MPa. Pauses of 24 hours at zero stress are placed at 1E3, 3E3, 6E3 and 1E4 cycles.

We note a softening, an increase in damping and strain accumulation for both tests as was already reported by Mandell [1], figure 5.a., figure 5.b. and figure 5.c. respectively.

Figure 5: Evolution of (a.) dynamic modulus. (b.) damping energy. (c.) mean strain. (d.) temperature.

Furthermore we recognise that the pauses do not influence the softening and the damping increase. However, as the mean strain recovers during the pauses, the initial trend is followed after restart of the test. Also the temperature quickly rises after each pause to follow its evolution due to fatigue damage, figure 5.d.

We conclude that the measured softening and the increased damping is not the result of heating. In fact, we can relate the softening and the damping increase to fatigue damage which is growing progressively during the test.

Fracture surfaces

Observation of fatigue fracture surfaces helps to understand the fatigue failure mechanisms. Especially cryogenically broken specimens are a good tool to identify damage occurred in tensile or fatigue tests

By carrying out fractographic studies, we find mainly three different kinds of fracture surfaces for the PBT-PET GF30. Firstly, we observe areas which show a fragile fracture surface, later referred as surface A. The matrix breaks in a brittle way and no signs of shear rupture are found. At low magnifications, flat plateaux of matrix material are found where fibres are pulled out and leave a neat hole in the counterpart, figure 6.a. At higher magnifications, the matrix material shows some roughness, figure 6.b. This kind of surface is often found for rapid failures [2-3].

Figure 6: Surface A ; fragile behaviour at a magnification of (a.) x 200. (b.) x 3000.

Secondly, we observed areas which show ductile behaviour, later referred as surface B. At a low magnification, fibres are also pulled out but seem to have deformed the matrix material around. Extensive drawing and necking of the matrix shows that the main failure mechanism is shear rupture, figure 7.a. At higher magnifications, the torn matrix material shows its big deformations especially in comparison to the fragile fracture, figure 7.b.

Figure 7: Surface B ; ductile behaviour at a magnification of (a.) x 200. (b.) x 3000.

Thirdly, there are areas which show the topology of a fragile rupture at low magnifications, figure 8.a. The fibres are pulled out neatly and did not deform the matrix during the failure process. However, at high magnifications we observe a fine structure of fibrils, figure 8.b. This kind of fracture will be referred to as surface C.

Figure 8: Surface C ; (a.) Quasifragile behaviour at x 200. (b.) Microfibrils at x 3000.

A virgin specimen is cryogenically broken in a tensile experiment at a crosshead speed of 500 mm/min. This ensures that no viscoelastic effects are taking place. For this kind of test we obtained a fragile fracture surface like surface A.

In the following, some fracture surfaces will be presented and discussed. The shown surfaces correspond to 3 x 4.2 mm of the complete fracture surface which measures 3 x 30 mm. It was only in this section that special features were observed. The rest of the surface breaks in a brittle way as surface A.

Figure 9: Fracture surface of tensile test (a.) specimen P1. (b.) micronotched specimen.

The result for the tensile test P1 mentioned before is shown in figure 9.a. for a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. Only a little amount breaks in a ductile way as surface B while the rest breaks fragile as surface A. Another tensile test was carried out after having grinded a micronotch at the border in the centre of the specimen, illustration at the top of figure 9.b. The notch is grinded with a carbon micro disc and its dimensions are 0.05 x 0.4 mm. The fracture surface reflects much more of a ductile zone, surface B. As the only changed parameter is the notch factor, it is assumed that the stress concentration is responsible for the increase of the ductile area. When the specimen is stressed, firstly, the highest stressed part of the specimen is surpassing the yield limit which will result in the formation of a ductile fracture surface. When the tensile force rises further, the rest of the stressed volume reaches the yield limit and the whole composite starts to break at a high velocity which will reduce yield effects and lead to a fragile fracture surface. As the stress concentration is more pronounced for the micronotched specimen, the amount of ductile fracture surface is larger as presented in the sketches figure 10.a. and figure 10.b.

Figure 10: Sketch of stress distribution (a.) plain specimen. (b.) micronotched specimen.

Figure 11.a. presents a fatigue fracture surface at $\sigma_a = 33$ MPa. Further studies showed that the other two tested stress levels produce nearly identical results. The fracture surface is quite different than the statically broken ones but with some similarities. For this test, fracture surface C is present at the left side of the specimen. At its boundary we find the ductile fracture surface B and the rest of the specimen is broken in a brittle way as surface A. We already anticipate that surface C corresponds to a macrocrack, some evidence will be given in the next chapter. As surface C is a macrocrack, the big amount of ductile surface B is again due to the stress concentration as for the micronotched specimen, figure 11.b.

Figure 11: Fatigue test at $\sigma_a = 33$ MPa (a.) fracture surface. (b.) stress distribution.

Figure 12: Cryofractures (a.) penny shaped crack. (b.) damage on fibre flanks. (c.) fibre at 0 cycles.

To identify the fatigue damage which is occurring during the fatigue test lifetime, we ruptured a specimen which was broken in a fatigue test at other locations. Damage is occurring on the fibres in loading direction. Firstly, there were found penny like cracks at the ends of the fibres, figure 12.a. Secondly, we found damage in the matrix on the fibre flanks, figure 12.b. For the cryogenic tensile test we could not find these damages: While fibres in loading direction and flush with the matrix like in figure 12.a. cannot be found, the matrix on the fibre flanks is broken in a rather brittle way, figure 12.c.

Replica technique

The replica technique allows us to identify superficial microcracks with a resolution of one micron. We took replicas at 0, 2E34, 4E4, 6E4, 8E4 12E4, 13E4 13.53 E4 cycles while the rupture was happening 944 cycles after taking the last replica. The SEM observation of the replicas showed, that a macrocrack is appearing at the end of the fatigue test. The macrocrack was occurring in the corner of the front and the right side. Figure 13.a.-d. shows the concerned surfaces before the test and at the very end of the test. A thermographic image shows the local heating of the macrocrack.

Figure 13: (a.-d.) Replicas for 0 and 135000 cycles (e.) Fracture surface 135944 cycles.

When we compare the last replicas with the fracture surface, we see that surface C corresponds to a macrocrack, figure 13.e.

CONCLUSIONS

The fibres of the PBT-PET GF30 are mainly oriented in Mouldflow direction. For this kind of orientation we find that damage is happening in the matrix close to the fibres lying in loading direction. Firstly, we observe penny shaped cracks at the fibre ends. Secondly, we find damage in the matrix surrounding fibre flanks. These damages are probably due to the high stresses [2-3] and the missing sizing at the fibre end. The fatigue damage is growing progressively and results in a softening, an increase in damping and a strain accumulation. At the end of the test, the microcracks coalesce into a macrocrack which was observed by the replica technique. The reduction of the section and mainly the stress concentration result in a local yielding of the matrix in the last cycle. The redistribution and further rise of applied force raises the stress in the rest of the section and the whole specimen breaks rapidly which does no longer permit the matrix to yield.

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